

Burnout & Stress Reduction in Psychiatric Nurses Through Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction Interventions

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Background

- Over 20 million HCW are at risk for MHP in the US due to demanding work environments
- 93% of HCW endorse being stressed out, 82% feel mentally and physically drained, 45% report not receiving adequate emotional support
- Per the U.S. Dept of Labor, nursing is ranked six out of 873 professions who experience work-related mental distress while working
- BO and stress among PNs has been evaluated to be higher among other nursing specialties
- MBSR interventions can be effective to relieve a HCWs mental unrest

Problem

The problem this project addressed was the lack of MBSR interventions to reduce burnout and stress in the psychiatric nurse who works in a psychiatric inpatient and crisis stabilization setting

Purpose & Aim

To decrease the experience of Burnout and Stress with the implementation of MBSR interventions in psychiatric nurses who work in a CSU and IPU at a psychiatric inpatient hospital

Aims: (a) identify causes of BO and stress in PNs (b) assess changes in BO and stress levels before and after the implementation of MBSR interventions (c) make recommendations for management of burnout and stress reduction for the PN

Methods

- Design:** pretest-posttest, single-group interventional design
- Setting:** private community-based teaching hospital located in Orange County
- Participants:** Psychiatric RNs, LVNs, PNAs
- Data Collection:** Data collected anonymously via Qualtrics QR code link

Results

MBSR Intervention deep breathing (N=348) was used most often, as well as muscle stretching (N=219)

- Statistically significant differences observed between pre- and post- means for emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and perceived stress
- No statistically significant difference observed in personal accomplishment

Framework

Conceptual Framework for Comfort Theory Applied to Psychiatric Nurses

Discussion

- EE was considered moderate to high, DP low, PA high pre- vs. post-implementation
- Nursing shortages may have affected the EE levels of PNs
- Level of burnout and stress was reduced among those who utilized daily MBSR
- MBSR lower stress by improving emotional regulation, self-confidence, and self-assurance.

Limitations

- Limited number of surveys collected
- Small sample size limits external validity
- Promotion of negative association between BO and stress levels limited positive emotional response

Recommendations

- Ongoing educational programs to develop optimistic attitudes toward psychiatric nursing environments
- The engagement of individual and institutional collaboration in reducing BO and stress through MBSR interventions may propel favorable effects on individual health, patient outcomes, and organizational success

Conclusions

- The use of MBSR interventions, such as deep breathing, muscle stretching, music therapy, and meditation, reduced the levels of burnout and stress in the PN
- Implementing MBSR interventions to reduce burnout and stress applies to psychiatric IP hospitals and many other nursing specialties
- It is critical to meet the unmet needs of the psychiatric nurse through the framework of Kolcaba's theory of comfort

References

